

Tracing the Transformation of the Labour Market through Historical Job Advertisements

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The JobAds project (FWF P35783) aims to investigate the transformation of the labour market by extracting and analysing job advertisements from historical newspapers between 1850-1950. Using Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, we focus on identifying and analysing various aspects of job advertisements, including positions offered and searched for, required skills, or media strategies within a corpus of 29 digitised newspaper titles from the ANNO corpus (Österreichische Nationalbibliothek, 2021). Through this analysis, we aim to gain valuable insights into

the development of the labour market and shed light on the historical dynamics of employment.

Analysing historical job advertisements presents unique challenges, starting with the need for high-quality machine-readable textual data. Errors in Optical Layout Recognition (OLR) and Optical Character Recognition (OCR), as identified in previous research (Jarlbrink and Snickars, 2017; Late and Kumpulainen, 2021; Torget, 2023; Wevers, 2023), pose problems for further text processing, including POS-tagging or dependency parsing. We plan to investigate the impact of OCR quality on the performance of NLP tasks, which was already an important topic in several studies (Rodriguez et al. 2012; Strien et al. 2020). Comparison and evaluation of the performance of different NLP tasks on raw OCR output and post-corrected text in our specific corpus will provide new valuable information about the necessity of time-consuming post-corrections for specific use cases.

Previous studies have employed text-mining approaches to examine job advertisements, e.g. for exploring ‘green jobs’ in Austria (Schober and Füllsack, 2017), or for analysing and classifying jobs in the printed medium *Kleine Zeitung* from the period 1950-2000 (Schober et al., 2015). However, analysing historical job advertisements introduces additional challenges due to language variations, including spelling, abbreviations, and period-specific linguistic styles. These challenges require special attention and a contextual understanding for an accurate interpretation. We must also account for the human factor, from misplaced job advertisements to content rotation either by mistake, or due to space-saving practices.

Ensuring the reliability and transparency of results is another important aspect considered in our project. In the current phase, we identified two main potential sources of bias: external factors stemming from the historical reality (newspapers were only one of several channels to realise matches of job seekers and vacancies (Wadauer et al., 2012); some newspapers contain extracts from other newspapers titles which leads to uncertainty about representativeness of a title for the area it was published in etc.), and factors related to processing digitised newspapers (different scan quality leading to non-consistent OCR results; some fonts posing greater problems for recognition than others etc.). Digitised newspapers as a research source are highly specific and a transparent interpretation of results can typically be further hindered by the incompleteness of digitised collections (Wijfjes, 2017), lack of metadata (Oberbichler and Pfanzelter, 2023) or transparency in the interfaces of digitised newspapers (Pfanzelter et al., 2021). Therefore, it is crucial to be aware of these limitations, document them and carefully consider the research questions that can be answered based on the available data (Torget, 2023).

To overcome these challenges, we have devised a series of plans and methodologies. In the initial phase, we focused on evaluation and further improvements of layout analysis and OCR results, and employed an automated approach to filter out pages which are unrelated to our research questions. Once we obtain high-quality machine-re-

adable data, we will analyse the structure and content of job advertisements, separately examining job descriptions and communication parts, as identified in (Misera, 2023). We plan to apply various NLP tasks, often in combination with machine learning techniques. By using BERT models pre-trained on historical texts (e.g. hmBERT (Schweter et al. 2022)), we can investigate how these can be adapted for specific use cases, such as job ads identification or post-OCR corrections, and compare them to classical dictionary- or rule-based approaches. Other NLP tasks include linguistic analysis to link job positions with verb-based descriptions of activities, parts-of-speech analysis, exploring abbreviations and interpunction usage, word embeddings, analysing word frequencies, and using topic modelling to gain insights into desired qualifications, requirements and responsibilities associated with different positions, employment trends and changing demand for specific skills and occupations. By examining patterns and trends over time, we can gain insights into the changing dynamics of employment and identify shifts in the demand for specific occupations and skills.

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